

Distributed Power Systems and FACTS

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Abstract

The intergration of renewable energy generators together with FACTS will play a major role in both conventional power transmission as well as current or voltage control, power quality, load flow control and communication controls in the evolution of the smart grid. There is a great need in the off-grid and microgrid arena for effective power flow control and technologies that enable better efficiency of these grids. The UPFC is seen as a device that can, amongst others, assist in novel developments in this field.

Introduction

Flexible AC Transmission Systems Technology (FACTS) was first proposed in the mid 80's. University curricula rapidly adjusted to include Power Electronics during this era with an emphasis on FACTS, High Voltage Direct Current and Power Convertors in to their Power System course streams. This was deemed essential for a new generation of appropriately enabled Power Systems engineers. In contrasts to developments in Variable Speed Drives, HVDC, and generalised Power Convertors, FACTS technology has failed to keep pace. Researchers suggest this as due mostly because of market uncertainties , especially by a very tough regulatory environment as well as transmission business volatility during this period (Hingorani 2007). FACTS devices depend on real-time data and control strategies in order to be effective in an operational environment. This was not widely available during the mid 80's. Today the emerging Smart Grid infrastructure consist of advanced digital technologies and IT technologies with sensing, monitoring and communications systems. These advanced IT/Telecoms technologies and features will enable FACTS devices to provide seamless real-time control and automation. On the other hand FACTS devices for the Smart Grid deployment need to be compatible with the Smart Grid advanced digital infrastructure and be capable of interacting with other Smart Grid devices which includes the equipment for sensing, monitoring and communications. According to (Hingorani 2007), FACTS technology can provide loading control of the network, stability and also voltage control. FACTS have the ability to improve the transmission capacity that is available for any particular facility as well as facilities that are new or under upgrade. Potentially for the future, if economically viable short-time storage comes of age, FACTS devices would also enable system restart and rapid frequency control.

FACTS technology in smart and microgrid power flow

FACTS is a system which integrates power electronic-based technology, i.e., solid state devices, to control bulk power flows in transmission systems. In other words, it integrates the modern power electronics technology with traditional power system technology. It uses static control equipment to contain changes in the electric transmission systems or operating conditions while maintaining sufficient steady-state and transient margins (Yu 2014).

The value that FACTS can bring into a system are (Yu 2014):

- Improves the flexibility of power flow control, keeps the flow in desired routes, avoids under-loading and over-loading in transmission lines.
- Increases power transfer capability of the transmission system to its maximum limit
- Enhances voltage and transient stability.

The values above are essential to maintain the smart-grid stability, and especially for facilitating the integration of renewable and demand responses. To control the parameters of transmission networks, such as, series impedance, shunt impedance, phase angle, thyristor-based controllers can be used which can be applied individually or simultaneously. A very useful control element in microgrid and smart grid systems is a UPFC.

Fig 1 Unified power flow controller complex power injection

In designing a FACTS based power flow intervention circuit, the UPFC can be employed not only in larger distribution networks, but may find equally suitable applications in the micro grid and smart grid arena. In figure 1 a typical UPFC circuit is shown. This shunt/series connection between two busses can effectively improve the conditions imposed by increased loading at bus 2. The power injection model is arrived as follows, assuming a current is capable of flowing from Bus A (i) to Bus B (j)

$$I_{ij} = (V_i + V_{s1} - V_j)y_{ij}$$

where V_{s1} is the injected series voltage between Bus A (i) and Bus B(j)

$$I_T^* = \frac{Re[V_{s1}I_{ij}^*]}{V_i}$$

and I_T is drawn by the circuit, I_q the reactive part, and I_{sh} the capacitor charging current in the shunt.

$$S_i = P_i + jQ_i = V_i I_{ij}^* + V_i (I_T + jI_q)^* + \sum_{i=1 \neq j}^n V_i I_{in}^* + V_i I_{sh}^*$$

$$S_{ig} = S_i^0 - S_i = \{V_i V_{s1}^* y_{ij}^* + V_i (I_T + jI_q)^*\}$$

$$S_{jg} = S_j^0 - S_j = V_j V_{s1}^* y_{ij}^*$$

$$P_{ig} = -Re(V_i V_{s1}^* y_{ij}^*) - V_i I_T^*$$

$$Q_{ig} = V_i I_q - Im(V_i V_{s1}^* y_{ij}^*)$$

A UPFC is therefore presented as a source of complex powers at the Bus A (i) and Bus B (j) of the network. At 50/60Hz, the largest portion of electricity simply flows along the path which has the lowest impedance. The lower impedance line this may get overloaded easily and the high impedance line under-loaded. FACTS technology has the aptitude to exactly control and continuously adjust the path reactance of a transmission line by adding parallel or series capacitors and inductors to the transmissions lines. FACTS technology makes it possible to direct and maintain constant power flow along a exact path in a constantly changing environment, including the load levels.

Figure 2. Complex Power insertion of UPFC

$$S_{ig} = P_{ig} + jQ_{ig} \text{ at bus } - i$$

$$S_{jg} = P_{jg} + jQ_{jg} \text{ at bus } - j$$

Smart-Grid Characteristics and FACTS

There are six major characteristics of a smart-grid (Yu 2014), maximizing the transmission assets, advance the operation efficiency and provide power system self-healing ability are among the key characteristics. All the previous mentioned require the latest technology to reduce transmission losses, balance the transmission loads, and restore grid stability rapidly as needed (Yu 2014). The requirement for special control mechanisms to be implemented is therefore vital. Many AC transmission lines can only deliver about one third of their maximum loading capacity due to power network safety concerns. The safety and stability concerns of power systems is the main factor in limiting the delivery capacity of the power-grids. Therefore, enhancing the stability of power grids is one way for increasing the capacity of transmission lines.

Power systems have to deal with two important control problems. One is to maintain its transient stability, i.e., maintain the synchronization between generators following a severe disturbance (Yu 2014). The other one is to maintain steady voltage under normal operating and disturbed conditions, i.e., voltage regulation. Effective controllers for enhancing the stability need to be implemented to actively damp the post-fault power and voltage oscillations.

Current Markets and future development

According to (Jawad & Hussein 2015), the global flexible AC transmission system is valued at USD 9885 million in 2015 and is predictable to reach USD 1.26 billion by 2020. A considered increase in market is expected in the next five years due to the fact that there is a growing acceptance of FACTS in application such as renewables, electric utilities, industrial and oil and gas. The objective of their research study was to analyse the market trends for each of the industries, growth rates of the various industry. The size of the flexible AC transmission systems (FACTS) market is given on the basis of the four geographical regions, namely; America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, and the rest of the world, where the region of America is estimated to hold the major share.

The future of FACTS can be achieved by introducing new technologies in association with different computational solutions; and combining existing FACTS devices. A more advance control system will improve the operation of FACTS devices.

To reduce the cost of FACTS devices and extend their operation, improvements in semiconductor technology needs to be done.

According to Jawad & Hussein (Jawad & Hussein, 2015), to achieve a high voltage transmission system around the world where electrical energy will be economically and environmentally friendly the key lies in FACTS and future improvements, such as:

Functional flexibility requires a FACTS device to provide more than one control function or control possibility. In addition, the FACTS device should be expandable to realize interconnections with other FACTS devices or storage devices. Connectivity requires FACTS and HVDCs with the ability to provide possibilities to connect with other power system control devices.

Other features of this future development is shown below in table 1:

Table 1 : Comparisons condensed from information after Jawad and Hussein, 2015.

<p>Structural Modularity and Scalability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The design of IBM's 360-mainframe computer is a good example for explaining modularity. The IBM system was designed to have various parts, called modules. The modules were designed and produced independently of one another, but, when combined, they worked together seamlessly. new modules could be added to the system, and old ones upgraded without rewriting code or disrupting operations. •Scalability implies performance.
<p>Functional Flexibility and Connectivity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Functional flexibility requires a FACTS device to provide more than one control function or control possibility. In addition, the FACTS device should be expandable to realize interconnections with other FACTS devices or storage devices. Connectivity requires FACTS and HVDCs with the ability to provide possibilities to connect with other power system control devices.

Conclusion

This paper discussed the advantages of FACTS technology for Smart-Grid and microgrid applications.

FACTS devices are compelling candidates for power flow control. By producing a series compensating voltage which can effectively change transmission line impedances. FACTS devices may be applied to problems such as minimizing real power losses and controlling system voltages after they have become too high; modulate network parameters to optimize power delivery, maximize the load ability, reduce power and voltage swing and fluctuation, and enhance grid stability, especially with the heavy integration of renewable energy sources.

It easy to observe there is growing in the market for FACTS technology and we expected it is continuing growth in the next decade.

References

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